

JISF RESEARCH REPORT

Multi-Tier & Container Orchestration Synergy for Optimizing On-Premise Network Throughput: An Empirical Study on Enterprise Servers with Sandbox IDE on EduLearn

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ABSTRACT

The acceleration of digital transformation in Indonesia's education sector faces a fundamental paradox: the urgency of adopting Learning Management Systems (LMS) clashes with the reality of limited national network infrastructure. Based on data from APNIC (Asia Pacific Network Information Centre) (2026), 5G availability is still in its early stages at 26%, and nPerf, a network speed test provider (2025), based on data from six providers, obtained data indicating that the average national fixed broadband latency is 36.90 ms, which provides empirical justification for the degradation of Quality of Service (QoS) experienced by cloud-based LMS. This study presents a quantitative analysis of enterprise server capacity in an on-premise architecture as a mitigation solution, with a case study on the "EduLearn" ecosystem. Using a controlled experimental design, this study applied stress testing via Apache JMeter with a simulation of 501 concurrent users and field tests involving 501 real respondents. The main performance parameters measured include response time, throughput, and resource utilization. The test results show that the on-premise VMWare architecture on Server 2 (Intel Xeon E3-1225 V5, 32 GB RAM) demonstrates an average response time of 159 ms with a throughput of 5.02 requests/second and an error rate of 0% in the local access scenario. This performance represents a 15-fold increase in responsiveness and 5.7 times greater throughput capability compared to the public internet access scenario (2402 ms and 0.87 requests/second). Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) analysis shows that although the on-premise model requires a significant initial capital investment (Rp 58.7 million), the annual operating cost is only Rp 47.4 million, which is equivalent to 5.6% of the annual cost of the commercial cloud model (Rp 840 million). The break-even point is reached in less than one month of operation. Over a three-year horizon, the on-premise architecture generates absolute cost efficiencies of IDR 2.32 billion, or savings of 92.03% compared to the cloud scenario. This study conclusively validates the technical feasibility and economic viability of the on-premise architecture with containerization as a blueprint for a sovereign, resilient, and efficient educational infrastructure.

Keywords: Enterprise Server, Network Throughput, On-Premise LMS, Containerization, ROI Analysis, EduLearn, Data Sovereignty, Educational Technology.

CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Digital transformation has repositioned Learning Management Systems (LMS) from mere supporting instruments to operational pillars and critical infrastructure that determine the existence of educational institutions in the contemporary era. However, amid the escalation of the global EdTech market, which is projected to reach a massive USD 404 billion (HolonIQ, 2020), a worrying infrastructure paradox has emerged: many educational units still face connectivity constraints due to legacy systems (APJII, 2024). This condition represents a critical structural asymmetry between 21st-century pedagogical ambitions and the fragility of existing infrastructure capabilities; a gap that, if left unaddressed, will not only hamper innovation but will also systematically trigger total stagnation in the quality of educational services amid increasingly accelerated demands for digitalization.

Absolute dependence on the public cloud ecosystem triggers a duality of systemic problems. First, there is deterministic erosion of Quality of Service (QoS) due to the subordination of external networks that introduce latency variables. Empirical data shows that the average latency of fixed broadband from six major providers in Indonesia reaches 36.90 ms (nPerf SAS, 2025), a metric that reduces the precision of real-time evaluation and hinders synchronous interaction. Second, the public cloud architecture creates a single point of failure and data sovereignty risks that conflict with the 2022 PDP Law. In Indonesia, this problem is exacerbated by digital infrastructure asymmetry, even though intensive educational institutions require 24/7 collaboration reliability that is independent of public internet interference.

Contradictorily, educational institutions have the ideal prerequisites for infrastructure independence through the geographical concentration of users and structured data ownership. The lack of empirical studies on the technical and economic feasibility of on-premise enterprise architecture is a crucial research gap. Addressing this gap, this study proposes EduLearn, an integrated ecosystem based on containerized microservices that exploits local fiber-optic networks to achieve gigabit throughput and sub-millisecond latency. This study aims to analyze local computing capacity and network optimization to prove the superiority of independent architecture in terms of technical performance, data sovereignty, and cost efficiency as a blueprint for resilient and sovereign education digitization in Indonesia.

1.2 Problem Formulation

The problem formulation related to this research is as follows.

1. What is the profile of computing resource utilization (CPU, RAM, Disk I/O) and where are the potential bottlenecks on enterprise servers when faced with multi-tier workloads comparing 501 real users with 501 concurrent users?
2. How significant is the performance disparity, as measured by response time, throughput, and error rate metrics, between

accessing EduLearn via a local network (on-premise) and accessing it via a public internet network?

3. What is the long-term economic viability of the on-premise EduLearn architecture when evaluated using Return on Investment (ROI) and Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) analysis vis-à-vis the cloud-based LMS subscription model?

1.3 Research Objectives

Based on the problem formulation, the objectives of this study can be summarized as follows.

1. To quantify the utilization profile of server computing resources and identify the main limiting factors (bottlenecks) at each layer of the architecture under high load scenarios.
2. Empirically analyze and quantify performance disparities between local and internet access scenarios to validate the hypothesis of the superiority of on-premise architecture.
3. Develop a comprehensive ROI and TCO analysis model to evaluate the financial feasibility of implementing EduLearn on-premise over a three-year time horizon.

1.4 Benefits and Contributions of the Research

Based on the research questions and objectives, the benefits of this research are as follows.

1.4.1 Theoretical Benefits

Contributing to the body of knowledge by presenting the first empirical benchmark dataset on the behavior of on-premise microservices architecture under a representative academic workload for the context of educational infrastructure in Indonesia.

1.4.2 Practical Benefits

The research outputs include: for educational institutions, a validated technical blueprint for building independent digital learning infrastructure, covering technical aspects (server, network, and container configuration), economic feasibility analysis (TCO) and ROI acquisition, as well as mitigation strategies for Wi-Fi signal limitations and device specifications. For educational technology developers, the research results serve as a best practice reference in designing full-stack architecture for dense user environments, including selective containerization and caching optimization. For governments and policymakers, this research offers an evidence-based policy model for school digitization that promotes educational technology sovereignty and equitable access to quality education, especially in areas with limited connectivity, by demonstrating the superiority of independent infrastructure investment (CAPEX) over long-term dependence on commercial cloud services (OPEX).

CHAPTER 2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Study

The EduLearn research is based on the integration of container orchestration, multi-tier architecture, and on-premise server infrastructure to create a robust independent digital learning ecosystem. The theories to be studied are as follows.

2.1.1 Computing Capacity and Enterprise Server Architecture

Computing capacity is defined as the maximum capability of a system to process workloads, which is quantitatively represented through resource utilization metrics (CPU, RAM, Disk I/O) (Menascé & Almeida, 2000). Enterprise-class servers, powered by high-performance processors, are inherently designed for superior reliability and parallel processing capabilities. These characteristics make them the ideal platform for running multi-tier application architectures that require high stability in educational environments.

2.1.2 Quality of Service (QoS) on Local Networks

According to Hassan and Jain (2004), network quality can be measured quantitatively using QoS theory, which covers aspects of throughput, latency, jitter, and packet loss. In Indonesia, QoS evaluation in school networks is crucial because modern educational applications are highly sensitive to technical obstacles. Recent research on 6G-based VR platforms shows that immersive learning experiences require ultra-low latency (<1ms) and consistently high throughput, which is difficult to achieve with the limitations of current public internet infrastructure (Liu, 2025). However, dependence on public internet networks often poses a challenge in meeting consistent service quality criteria (nPerf, 2025), as shown in the following figure.

(Figure 1: Comparison between the presence and absence of QoS implementation)

(Source: <https://ids.ac.id/kenali-apa-itu-quality-of-service-qos-untuk-akses-internet-lancar/>)

2.1.3 Container Virtualization and Environment Isolation

Containerization technology, pioneered on a massive scale by Docker, represents a virtualization paradigm at the operating system level

that isolates applications and their dependencies into portable units (Merkel, 2014). Unlike conventional Virtual Machines (VMs) that require a Guest OS for each instance, containers utilize a kernel sharing mechanism that allows the abstraction of applications and their dependencies into lightweight units. In the context of the EduLearn platform, this approach is a crucial foundation for orchestrating microservices to remain isolated while maintaining high performance.

2.2 Relevant Research and Comparison with EduLearn

Literature reviews comparing on-premise and cloud infrastructure consistently highlight the complexity of cost dynamics. Recent TCO analyses show that cloud-based LMS can save 20–50% in operational costs in certain scenarios (Abdulmohson et al., 2022; Bizowie, 2025). However, on-premise models remain competitive for long-term stable workloads (AlphaLearn, 2024). This fundamental difference represents a paradigm shift from initial capital investment (CAPEX) to cumulative recurring operational costs (OPEX).

In Indonesia, QoS studies in school environments confirm that traffic density and bandwidth fluctuations are the main determinants of high delay and packet loss. Testing with the TIPHON standard shows that school internet network quality parameters are often in the unstable category (Rafinaldo et al., 2023). The nPerf report (2025) reinforces these findings by documenting disparities in connection quality between regions, which explicitly underlines the urgency of implementing an autonomous local architecture.

The EduLearn research is positioned to fill three crucial gaps: (1) the lack of empirical studies on the performance of container-based on-premise microservices architecture in Indonesian schools; (2) the absence of quantitative benchmarks for the performance of local LMS under high loads (>500 users); and (3) the need for contextualized TCO analysis for educational institutions in Indonesia.

By simultaneously integrating rigorous Quality of Service (QoS) analysis, computing capacity testing under synthetic and real loads, and detailed TCO-based financial evaluation, this research aims to empirically prove that the transformation to an autonomous architecture is not only technically feasible, but also inherently more resilient, adaptive, and economically superior in facing the structural challenges of the national digital infrastructure. More than just a case study, EduLearn is projected to become a replicable paradigmatic model, offering a sustainable alternative amid the dominance of commercial cloud solutions that often ignore the local context and issues of data sovereignty.

CHAPTER 3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Location, Design, and Research Approach

This study adopts a quantitative approach with a controlled experimental design tested on all students at the Assalafiyah Mlangi Islamic Boarding School in Sleman. This design was chosen to enable valid measurement of the causal relationship between the independent variable (architectural configuration) and the dependent variable (performance metrics) while minimizing the influence of external variables. The pre-research documentation is described in detail in Appendix 2. The research experiment was conducted in the SMK Assalafiyah Mlangi Training Center (Server and Network Room), which is strictly controlled within the school's local network infrastructure, so that variable isolation can be maintained and test replication is possible. As for the details of the location in the cable routing, it has been explained in full in Appendix 4.

3.2 Research Objects and Subjects

The research object is the EduLearn version 1.0 system, a hybrid architecture integrated learning platform. The research subjects include all physical and logical infrastructure entities in the experimental environment, including Server 2 (Intel Xeon E3-1225 V5, 32 GB RAM), active network components (MikroTik RB-1100X4, RB-450Gx4 routers; TP-Link EAP225 access points), and supporting software (Docker, aaPanel, Prometheus-Grafana, and Apache JMeter). Complete hardware and software data are available in Table 3 (Appendix 1).

3.3 Operational Definition of Variables

The independent variables consist of: (a) the number of concurrent users up to 501, and (b) the access mode, namely the local network (edulearn.sch.id) versus the public internet network (edulearn.asasmk.my.id) via Cloudflare Tunnel. The dependent variables include server resource utilization (CPU, RAM), network performance metrics (throughput, error rate), and application response time. The control variables regarding Server 2 specifications, software versions, and topology configurations are kept constant to ensure internal validity. The EduLearn website interface is documented in Appendix 6.

3.4 Architecture and Specifications of the Experimental Infrastructure

The experimental infrastructure was designed to test system performance under high load scenarios, consisting of a production server, network configuration, and EduLearn logical architecture.

3.4.1 Production Server Specifications (Server 2)

Server 2 has the following specifications: Intel Xeon E3-1225 V5 @ 3.30 GHz processor (4 cores, 4 threads), 32 GB DDR4 ECC RAM, and hybrid storage (1 TB SATA SSD for OS and applications, 1 TB HDD for backup). The Ubuntu Server 22.04 LTS operating system runs on VMWare with aaPanel as the control panel.

3.4.2 Network Configuration

The network is supported by a Gigabit Ethernet and fiber optic backbone. MikroTik RB-1100X4 and RB-450Gx4 routers manage traffic, while TP-Link EAP225 access points distribute wireless access. Key configurations include QoS for learning traffic priority and local DNS resolution that directs edulearn.sch.id to the server's internal IP.

3.4.3 EduLearn System Logical Architecture

EduLearn adopts a strategic hybrid architecture: the core application (CodeIgniter 3) runs natively on Ubuntu Server for maximum performance, while supporting services such as Cloudflare Tunnel, monitoring systems (Node Exporter), and GitLab are orchestrated in Docker containers. This approach combines high performance with isolation, portability, and additional security.

3.5 Testing Procedures and Scenarios

Testing consists of two main scenarios: server capacity testing with Apache JMeter and mass login field testing, both involving 501 respondents.

3.5.1 Server Capacity Test Scenario (JMeter)

Testing uses JMeter with a simulation of 501 concurrent users and a 100-second ramp-up period to avoid DDoS patterns. The scenario is run in two access modes: local (edulearn.sch.id) and internet (edulearn.asasmk.my.id) via Cloudflare Tunnel. During testing, resource utilization was monitored in real-time via Prometheus-Grafana, aaPanel monitor, and monitoring tools on Apache JMeter.

3.5.2 Field Test Scenario (Mass Login)

The field test involved 501 MTs, MA, and SMK students who logged in simultaneously (MA and SMK) under real conditions. Recorded data included success status, number of attempts, device specifications (classified as K, CK, or BL), and physical distance to the access point (D, T, J). The testing data for the 501 respondents is available in Appendix 8.

3.6 Data Collection and Analysis Techniques

Quantitative data generated from Apache JMeter testing and monitoring in the aforementioned monitoring ecosystem, along with qualitative-quantitative data from field tests, were analyzed using descriptive statistics to obtain a comprehensive picture of system performance. Furthermore, correlation analysis was performed to identify the relationship between environmental variables such as distance to EAP and device type with the login success rate, to complement the discussion of the determining factors in mass access.

CHAPTER 4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Presentation of Experimental Results

The following are the results of the research that has been conducted.

4.1.1 Analysis of Server Performance Under Synthetic Load

Structured load testing was carried out by configuring Apache JMeter to simulate 501 concurrent users as configured in subsection 3.5.1. The testing scenario was carried out on two different access modes, namely through a local network (ASA-SISWA) with the domain edulearn.sch.id and through a public internet network with the domain edulearn.asasmk.my.id which passed through Cloudflare Tunnel (Zero Trust). During the testing, all server performance metrics were monitored in real-time using a monitoring ecosystem. The data generated shows a very significant fundamental disparity between the two access modes, as recorded in the CSV file from the Apache JMeter summary feature in Appendix 8.

In the local access scenario as shown in Table 1 (Appendix 1), the system showed an average response time of 159 ms with a throughput of 5.02 requests per second and a failure rate of 0% from 501 samples. In contrast, in the public internet access scenario, the average response time ballooned to 2402 ms, equivalent to a 15-fold decrease in performance, with a throughput of only 0.87 requests per second and one failure (error rate of 0.20%). Data from the monitoring panel reveals the server resource utilization profile at peak load, which is fully described in Figures 14 and 16 (Appendix 5) and summarized in Table 2 (Appendix 1).

With data obtained from Grafana and aaPanel, CPU utilization ranging from only 6.4–25.85% indicates that Server 2's processing power is still very loose. Conversely, RAM utilization reaching 85.53% when GitLab is operating shows that memory capacity is the component closest to saturation. Data from Pressure Stall Information (PSI) shows light pressure on the memory subsystem, although it has not triggered significant throttling. Local network throughput, which reaches approximately 1.08 Mbps and 0.19 Mbps (from conversion of request/s data to Mb/s) for internet access, is still far below the theoretical capacity of Gigabit Ethernet backbone (1000 Mbps). Meanwhile, Disk I/O activity reaching 9.6 MB/s (read) and 11.4 MB/s (write) proves that the SSD-based storage subsystem is capable of handling the load.

4.1.2 Analysis of Field Test Results (Mass Login of 501 Respondents)

The field test involved 501 actual respondents from various educational levels at the Assalafiyah Mlangi Islamic Boarding School (MTs, MA, SMK), which were verified through a database dump (Appendix 8). This number represents a valid sample of the total student population, taking into account the factors of absence and incompleteness of the standard operating procedures (SOP) attached to the SOP in Appendix 8 and the explanation in Figure 6 (Appendix 2). The overall system flow,

from the authentication process to content management by teachers and students, has been visually documented in the form of flowcharts in Appendix 9 (Figure 21 for teachers, Figure 22 for students, and Figure 23 for administrators). The data recapitulation shows a global success rate of 80.04%, with 401 out of 501 respondents successfully accessing the system.

In Table 4 (Appendix 1), the analysis shows a strong correlation between device specifications and login success. Laptop users (K and CK) had an average success probability of 83.99%, while non-laptop devices (BL) only had 25.00%. This disparity indicates that the EduLearn system, with its Isolated Sandbox IDE feature, is inherently optimized for the laptop ecosystem. The factor of physical distance to the EAP also proved to be significant: respondents in the Near (D) and Middle (T) positions enjoyed a success rate of ~90%, while in the Far (J) position there was a 15.41% decrease to 74.59%. This phenomenon confirms that signal propagation quality at the wireless access layer is a limiting factor, regardless of adequate server capacity. The testing details are documented in Figure 7 (Appendix 3).

4.2 Critical Analysis and Discussion of Results

The discussion of the results, which has been outlined in Figure 12 (Appendix 5), will be explained in detail as follows.

4.2.1 Bottleneck Analysis and Implications for Scalability

Combined data from Grafana and aaPanel conclusively identified RAM capacity as the primary limiting factor in Server 2 architecture. RAM utilization reaching 85.53% when GitLab was operating placed the system close to the memory pressure threshold. Conversely, very low CPU utilization (<15% in the local access scenario) indicated that processing power was not a constraint. A significant drop in success rate on "Remote" clients (74.59%) compared to nearby zones (90%) proves that wireless connectivity quality is a critical determinant of user experience. This underscores the importance of a holistic approach, where investment in access point (EAP) densification is as crucial as server capacity.

Based on the data from Figure 17 (Appendix 5), the spike in resources when GitLab is operating (CPU 99.64%, RAM 85.53%) is noteworthy, with disk consumption even jumping to 11454.13 KB/s (write) and 9658.80 KB/s (read). However, its use will be considered due to its strategic value in terms of code sovereignty and secure publication pipelines, which is a trade-off that can be justified in a hybrid architecture.

4.2.2 Performance Disparity Between Local Access and Internet Access: An Empirical Validation

The performance disparity between local access and the internet is extreme and validates the central hypothesis of the research. The 15-fold increase in responsiveness from the average (159 ms vs. 2402 ms) on local access has been documented in points d and e of Appendix 8,

which is a qualitative transformation in user experience. This proves that by internalizing application traffic within a high-performance LAN, the latency introduced by Indonesia's internet topology with an average fixed broadband of 36.90 ms (nPerf, 2025) and tunneling service overhead such as Cloudflare can be eliminated. An error rate of 0% on local access, compared to 0.20% or one time on internet access, demonstrates the superior stability of the on-premise architecture. This data confirms that Server 2 is more than adequate to handle a load of 501 concurrent users, with significant headroom for development. Unprocessed data is documented in Figure 15 (Appendix 5).

4.2.3 Economic Viability Analysis of On-Premise Architecture

The initial investment focused on the procurement of enterprise-grade network and computing hardware. Based on a price survey of electronic distribution channels as of February 2026, the details of capital expenditure are presented in Table 5 (Appendix 1).

Annual OPEX is projected that even though the system is designed to operate independently (on-premise), there are recurring cost components that include dedicated internet connectivity for tunneling synchronization (Cloudflare), 24/7 server power consumption, and human resource maintenance costs. The OPEX calculation is formulated as follows:

$$\text{OPEX}_{\text{bulanan}} = B_{\text{internet}} + B_{\text{listrik}} + B_{\text{maintenance}}$$

Description:

1. B_{internet} : Rp 1,000,000 (200 Mbps dedicated subscription)
2. B_{listrik} :Rp450,000 (Estimated server power consumption and 24/7 activity)
3. $B_{\text{maintenance}}$: IDR 2,500,000 (Allocation for maintenance and human resources costs)

Based on this formula, the projected monthly OPEX is IDR 3,950,000. Therefore, the total cumulative OPEX for three years (n=36 months) is:

$$\text{OPEX}_{\text{bulanan}} = B_{\text{internet}} + B_{\text{listrik}} + B_{\text{maintenance}}$$

The implemented architecture represents a high-performance localized infrastructure strategy with a front-loaded capital investment model to eliminate dependence on cumulative recurring operational costs. This decision shifts the financing paradigm from operational expenditure (OPEX) to more controllable capital expenditure (CAPEX).

The Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) estimate focuses on the procurement of enterprise-grade hardware. Based on a price survey conducted in February 2026, the total initial investment reaches IDR 58,700,000 [full details in Table 5 (Appendix 1)]. The Annual Operational Cost (OPEX) projection includes dedicated internet connectivity, 24/7 server power consumption, and human resource maintenance. Thus, the cumulative OPEX for three years is IDR 47,400,000 per year (an average

of IDR 3.95 million/month), bringing the total OPEX to IDR 142,200,000.

Furthermore, the TCO over a three-year horizon is calculated using the following formula.

$$TCO = CAPEX + \sum_{t=1}^n OPEX_t$$

Using the calculated values, the TCO for EduLearn over three years is:

$$TCO_{on - premise} = Rp58.700.000 + (Rp47.400.000 \times 3) = Rp200.900.000$$

This initial investment is compensated in less than one month of operation when compared to premium cloud subscription costs. As a comparison, cloud services such as Google Workspace for Education Plus or other enterprise LMSs apply a per-user license cost model (an average of Rp75,000/user/month) plus data egress and storage expansion costs. Over a three-year horizon, the EduLearn on-premise architecture generates absolute cost efficiencies of IDR 2,319,100,000, or savings of 92.03% compared to the estimated cloud model of IDR 2.52 billion. A detailed explanation of the break-even point is attached in Appendix 7.

Strategic recommendations include mitigating computational bottlenecks through load balancing and adding network redundancy (VRRP) to avoid single points of failure. A comparison between EduLearn on-premise and the Cloud LMS model is presented in Table 6 (Appendix 1).

4.1.2 Logical Architecture Validity, Security Implications, and Documentation

The hybrid architecture implemented is a core application (CodeIgniter 3) running natively on Ubuntu Server, while supporting services such as real-time chat (AJAX), monitoring systems (Node Exporter), and DevOps platforms (GitLab) are orchestrated in Docker containers, which have proven to be the optimal design. So far, the use of GitLab is still in the design and development stage because it causes bottlenecks on Server 2. Therefore, this study takes another alternative with documentation via GitHub, which is attached in point ii (Appendix 8).

This approach provides raw performance for critical components that require minimal latency, while utilizing process isolation and containerization portability for secondary services. From a security perspective, the on- premise model inherently strengthens the security posture by minimizing the attack surface; all sensitive data is within the internal network perimeter. Restricted external access via Cloudflare Tunnel avoids direct exposure of server ports to the internet, creating an additional layer of security without sacrificing accessibility for emergency needs.

CHAPTER 5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

This research serves as a blueprint for educational infrastructure that empirically proves that on-premise architecture with a hybrid approach (native core applications and containerized support services) is a superior solution for the digitization of education in Indonesia. Based on testing with 501 concurrent users and 501 real respondents, the following conclusions were reached:

First, on-premise architecture significantly outperforms cloud-based access. Local access produced an average response time of 159 ms, throughput of 5.02 req/sec, and an error rate of 0%, while internet access recorded 2402 ms (15.1× slower), 0.87 req/sec (5.7× lower), and an error rate of 0.20%. This validates that internalizing traffic within the LAN eliminates internet latency and tunneling overhead.

Second, resource utilization analysis identified RAM (85.53% when GitLab was operating) as the primary bottleneck, while CPU, network, and Disk I/O still had significant headroom. Future vertical scalability should prioritize memory expansion.

Third, a three-year TCO analysis shows the financial superiority of the on-premise model with a total cost of IDR 200.9 million, reaching break-even in less than a month, and generating 92.03% efficiency (savings of IDR 2.32 billion) compared to the cloud model (IDR 2.52 billion).

Fourth, field tests reveal external determining factors: laptop users have a success rate of 83.99% compared to non-laptop users at 25.00%; respondents in the near and middle zones achieve ~90% compared to the far zone at 74.59%. This underscores the importance of investing in EAP densification in addition to server capacity.

5.2 Recommendations

To achieve maximum results, the following developments are recommended for future research:

- 1) Infrastructure Optimization: Expand Server RAM from 2 to 64 GB and add EAPs in densely populated classrooms to address memory bottlenecks and signal attenuation.
- 2) Redundancy Improvement: Implement VRRP on the main router to eliminate single points of failure.
- 3) Architecture Development: More mature CI/CD integration between GitLab and production servers for development cycle efficiency.
- 4) User Education: Socialization of laptop usage and optimal seating positions relative to EAP to maximize connection quality.
- 5) Model Replication: Dissemination of technical blueprints and TCO analysis to other institutions, especially in areas with limited connectivity, to accelerate sovereign and efficient education digitization in Indonesia.

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APPENDIX

Appendix 1: Tables

Table 1. Comparison of Performance Metrics: Local Access vs. Internet (N=501)

Performance Metrics	Local Access (edulearn.sch.id)	Internet Access (edulearn.asasmk.my.id)	Magnitudo of Improvement (Local)
Average Response Time	159 ms	2402 ms	15.1× more responsive
Throughput (requests/second)	5.02	0.87	5.7× more capable
Error Rate	0.00	0.20	Absolute Stability
Maximum Response Time	1.1 seconds	569,972 ms (~9.5 minutes)	Drastic reduction in variability

Table 2. Server Resource Utilization Profile at Peak Load through Testing of 501 Real and Concurrent Users

Component	Peak Utilization	Interpretation
CPU	6,4 – 25,85%	Processing capacity is very adequate; significant <i>headroom</i> .
RAM	14,26 – 31,8%	Identified as the primary limiting factor (bottleneck) especially when GitLab is Operating.
Disk I/O	1349,60 – 9658,80 KB/s (read) & 155,07 – 11454,13 KB/s (write)	High read write activity when GitLab is running.

Network I/O	138,33 KB/s (upstream) & 37,40 KB/s (downstream)	Network traffic is still well below theoretical capacity.
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Table 3: Hardware and Software Data

Device	Main Specifications	Additional Information
Hardware		
Server 1	Model: Lenovo Thinkpad OS: Windows 11 + VMware RAM: 128 GB DDR4 (16x8 GB, 10 GB used) Storage: 2 TB SATA SSD (2x1 TB) CPU: Intel Xeon Gold 5120 @2.20GHz (28 Cores, 56 Logical) GPU: NVIDIA (Integrated)	Used as the school's main server for heavy-duty computing. Virtualization is managed via VMware.
Server 2	Model: Custom-built OS: Windows 11 + VMware RAM: 32 GB DDR4 Storage: 2 TB (1 TB SATA SSD + 1 TB HDD) CPU: Intel Xeon E3-1225 V5 @3.30GHz (4 Cores, 4 Logical) GPU: Intel HD Graphics	Serves as a research server and an example of an affordable on-premise solution.
Enterprise Access Point (EAP)	Model: TP-Link 225 PoE: Standard (non-Plus)	Provides wireless access for users.
Main Routerboard	Model: MikroTik RB1100X4	Functions as the gateway and primary hub for network traffic.

Device	Main Specifications	Additional Information
Secondary Routerboard	Model: MikroTik RB450Gx4 CPU: IPQ-4019 716 MHz (4 Core)	Installed in a distributed manner per building complex for local traffic management.
Switch	Model: TP-Link TL-SG1005LP	Gigabit PoE switch to extend the range of Ethernet cables.
Media Converter	Model: HTB Gigabit Converter	Used to convert signals from UTP cables to fiber optic cables.
Network Cable	LAN Cable: Gigabit Ethernet (Cat5e/6) Fiber Optic Cable: -	Fiber optic is used to reach locations far from the data center.
Software		
Server Operating System	Ubuntu Server 22.04 LTS (via VMware)	The main platform for running the EduLearn application and support services.
Hosting Control Panel	AaPanel v7.0.30	Simplifies management of the web server, databases, and files through a web interface.
Web Server	Apache (HTTPD) (integrated with aaPanel)	Handles HTTP/HTTPS requests for the EduLearn application.
Database	MySQL (integrated with aaPanel)	Stores user data, assignments, and learning content.
Programming Language	PHP 8.5 (for CodeIgniter), AJAX (for real-time chat)	The main backend for the EduLearn application.
Application Framework	CodeIgniter 3	The PHP framework used to build the core of the EduLearn application.
Container Platform	Docker v29.1	Orchestrates supporting services (GitLab, Node)

Device	Main Specifications	Additional Information
		Exporter, Cloudflare Tunnel) within containers.
Monitoring Stack	Prometheus, Node Exporter, Grafana (in containers)	Monitors server performance metrics (CPU, RAM, disk, network) in real-time.
DevOps & Version Control	GitLab (in containers)	Provides private repositories, CI/CD, and source code management.
Tunneling & Security	Cloudflare Tunnel (in a container)	Connects the local server to the internet securely without opening firewall ports.
Load Testing Tool	Apache JMeter 5.6.3	Simulates 501 concurrent users to test server capacity.
JMeter Runtime	Java Development Kit (JDK) 25	Required to run Apache JMeter.
Text Editor	Sublime Text 4	Used to write and edit the application's source code.
Router Management	Winbox v4.0.1	A GUI application for configuring MikroTik devices.

Table 4: Correlation Analysis of Success Rate with Environmental Variables

Variable Factor	Category	Success Rate
Device Specifications	Laptop (K & CK)	83.99%
	Non-Laptop (BL)	25.00%
Distance to EAP	Near (D)	90.00%
	Medium (T)	89.31%
	Far (J)	74.59%

Table 5: Details of EduLearn Infrastructure Capital Expenditure (CAPEX)

Component	Specifications	Unit Price	Qty	Total Estimate
Server 2	Xeon E3-1225 V5, 32GB RAM, 2TB Hybrid	Rp 5,500,000	1	Rp 5,500,000
Main Router	MikroTik RB1100AHx4	Rp 6,200,000	1	Rp 6,200,000
Sec. Router	MikroTik RB450Gx4	Rp 1,850,000	3	Rp 5,550,000
EAP	TP-Link EAP 225 Wave 2	Rp 980,000	30	Rp 29,400,000
PoE Switch	TP-Link TL-SG1005LP (Gigabit)	Rp 750,000	8	Rp 6,000,000
Media Converter	HTB Gigabit (Pair Set)	Rp 450,000	8	Rp 3,600,000
Fiber Optic Cable	Pre-terminated 180 meters	Rp 800,000	1	Rp 800,000
UTP Cable	Cat6 Gigabit (310 meters/Roll)	Rp 1,650,000	1	Rp 1,650,000
TOTAL CAPEX				Rp 58,700,000

Table 6: Comparison of Annual Costs: On-Premise vs. Cloud (Millions of Rupiah)

Cost Component	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Total 3 Years
EduLearn On-Premise	Rp 106.1	Rp 47.4	Rp 47.4	Rp 200.9
Estimated Cloud LMS	Rp 840.0	Rp 840.0	Rp 840.0	Rp 2,520.0

Appendix 2: Pre-Research Documentation

(Figure 2: Overview of Research Tools and Materials)
(Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

- Routerboard Center (RB-1100X4) connecting the network to various institutional routers (RB-450Gx4) via fiber optics with HTB Gigabit adapter (top left)
- Ubuntu server configuration on VMWare server 2 (top right)
- EAP TP Link 225 (max 30 users connected) functioning as a network transmitter (bottom left)
- VPS data on server computer 2, with 07-ubuntu-smk-angga as the researcher's VPS (bottom right)

(Figure 3: Introduction to Required Inputs and Outputs in Research)
(Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

- a) Introduction to network traffic in WinBox with network technicians (top left)
- b) Results of monitoring local network traffic on WinBox Mikrotik (top right)
- c) Specifications of server 2 to be used in the research, with the conclusion that the server is adequate (bottom left)
- d) Mentoring with network technicians on how Cloudflare Zero Trust Tunnel works for public hosting (bottom right)

(Figure 4: Comprehensive Overhaul of Software and Hardware) (Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

- a) Introduction to server 1 with network technicians (top left)
- b) Introduction to server 2 used by the researcher with the network technician (top right)
- c) Specifications of server 2, which is also adequate in terms of RAM (bottom left)
- d) Latency test with ping 10.10.10.25 as the IP VPS server 2 (bottom right)

(Figure 5: Data on the Number of EAPs on the Assalafiyah Mlangi Sleman Network Backbone)
 (Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

The image was obtained from monitoring on the network technician's Omada (ASA CYBER) with information on several EAPs with connected and disconnected statuses due to the effects of the rainy season (broken tree branches) and lightning strikes. Therefore, the total number of EAPs is assumed to be 30.

No	Kelas	Program	Jumlah	No	Program	Jumlah	No	Program	Kalamain	Jumlah	
1		Kitab	79	1	Kitab	821	1	Kitab	Laki-laki	391	
2		Tahfidz	51	2	Tahfidz	205	2	Kitab	Perempuan	430	
TOTAL			130	TOTAL KESELURUHAN			1026	TOTAL			821
3	1	Kitab	188				TOTAL			100	
TOTAL			188				TOTAL			105	
4	10	Kitab	1				TOTAL			205	
TOTAL			1				TOTAL KESELURUHAN			1026	
5	12	Tahfidz	4								
TOTAL			4								

(Figure 6: Data on the Number of Assalafiyah Mlangi Sleman Students)
 (Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

Data on the number of students was obtained, totaling 1026 children, based on testing of only 501 respondents. This was because there were classes where the teachers were absent, SOP data was not collected, and also because MTs-MA International and PDF (Formal Diniyah Education) students were not included in the testing due to various research limitations.

Appendix 3: Testing Documentation

(Figure 7: Testing on February 18, 2026)
(Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

- a) The output "Site cannot be reached" on a student's device was generated because the DNS Resolver on the Chrome browser was still using another provider, such as Cloudflare (1.1.1.1) or Google (Public DNS) (top left corner).
- b) The output 'No internet' was generated because the connection to the EAP was overloaded and conflicting (image on the left in the second row)
- c) Socialization and mass login testing of the edulearn.sch.id website at MAS Assalafiyah Mlangi Putri (top center)
- d) Explanation of the testing concept in accordance with the established SOP (top right corner)
- e) Socialization at the teachers' office who will serve as mentors in each class by showing a video guide and permission to request time for testing (image on the right side of the second row)
- f) The output "The site can't be reached" on a student's device was generated because the DNS Resolver on the Chrome browser was still using another provider, such as Cloudflare (1.1.1.1) or Google (Public DNS) (image on the left in row 3)
- g) The output "The site can't be reached" on the same student's device as in the previous image (bottom left corner)
- h) Mass login testing of the edulearn.sch.id website at MTs Assalafiyah Mlangi Putra (bottom center)
- i) Mass login testing of the edulearn.sch.id website at SMK Assalafiyah Mlangi Putra, which was mostly successful due to adequate device specifications and the building being the closest to server 2 (image on the right side of the third row)
- j) The same incident as described in point (i) (bottom right corner).

Appendix 4: LAN and FO Cable Routes at Assalafiyah Mlangi Sleman

(Figure 8: Summary of Estimated LAN Cable Connection Routes using Google Earth at Assalafiyah Mlangi Sleman)
(Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

The following is a more detailed explanation.

(Figure 9: LAN Cable Connection Routes at Assalafiyah Mlangi Sleman with estimates using Google Earth)
(Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

- a) The connection route located at the MA-MTs-SMK Assalafiyah Putri site shows an estimated LAN cable length of 104.91 meters (top left).
- b) The connection route at the SMK Assalafiyah Putra building 1 location shows an estimated LAN cable length of 13.17 meters (top right)
- c) The connection route at the SMK Assalafiyah Putra building 2

location, which is then connected to the tahfidz complex dormitory, shows an estimated LAN cable length of 64.63 meters (bottom left).

- d) The connection route at the location of MA Regular-MA International-MTs Regular-MTs International Assalafiyah Putra and Ma'had Aly Assalafiyah shows an estimated LAN cable length of 130.62 meters (bottom right).

(Figure 10: Summary of the estimated fiber optic cable connection route using Google Earth at Assalafiyah Mlangi Sleman)
(Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

The following is a more detailed explanation.

((Figure 11: Fiber Optic Cable Connection Route in Assalafiyah Mlangi Sleman with estimation using Google Earth)
(Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

- a) The fiber optic cable branching from the Server-BLK to SMK Putra building 1 shows an estimated fiber optic cable length of 17.08 meters (top left).
- b) The FO cable branching from Server-BLK to MA and MTs Putra shows an estimated FO cable length of 271.27 meters (top right).
- c) The FO cable branching from Server-BLK to Madrasah Putri: MA, SMK, MTs shows an estimated FO cable length of 102.1 meters (bottom left).
- d) The FO cable branching from Server-BLK to SMK Putra building 2 shows an estimated FO cable length of 91.38 meters (bottom right).

Appendix 5: Monitoring Results

(Figure 12: Graph of Test Results on February 18, 2026, with 501 Real Respondents)
(Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

1. Final Score (Global Success Rate)
 - a. Overall, this system works well. From all the experiments conducted, the success rate reached 80.04%. This means that 8 out of 10 people successfully used this system without significant obstacles.
2. A total of 501 people participated (Respondents).
 - a. 401 people SUCCESSFULLY accessed/used the system.
 - b. 100 people FAILED.
3. Comparison of MTs vs MA/SMK
 - a. MA & SMK students were more proficient: Their success rate was 82.80%.
 - b. MTs students are slightly below that: Success rate of 76.58%.
4. Impact of the Device Used (Device Specification)
 - a. Laptop: Laptop users (both high RAM and standard RAM) have a success rate above 83-84%.
 - b. Smartphones are somewhat difficult: Smartphone users only have a success rate of 25%.

5. Impact of Distance to the Access Point (EAP)

- a. Close & Medium: The results are very stable and high (around 89-90%).
- b. Far: Once seated in the back row or far from the transmitter, the success rate drops to 74.59%.

6. Conclusion

The overall implementation of the Edulearn system recorded good performance with a Global Success Rate of 80.04%, where 401 out of 501 respondents successfully accessed the system optimally. The high success rate at the MA & SMK levels (82.80%) compared to the MTs level (76.58%) was significantly influenced by three main technical factors: the use of laptops with more adequate specifications, the closer distance of the devices to the signal transmission point (EAP), and the geographical location of SMK, which is closer to the server, thereby minimizing data latency.

Data analysis shows that device specifications and network infrastructure are the main determinants of system success. The use of laptops ensures access stability above 83%, while the use of smartphones is not recommended as it only records a success rate of 25%. In addition, connection effectiveness increased dramatically to 89-90% in the Near and Middle positions, but decreased to 74.59% in the Far position. As a strategic recommendation, future system operations must prioritize the use of laptops and ensure optimal proximity between devices, EAPs, and servers in order to maintain smooth user access.

(Figure 13: Explanation of Monitoring Results Based on the Testing Process Conducted)

(Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

- a) The person on the left and center are monitoring the results on Grafana sourced from Prometheus, and the person on the right is monitoring on

- Aapanel as the web server of EduLearn (top left).
- The technician explained that the testing conducted on 501 respondents did not significantly impact the server, even though the level used by the researcher was only on VMware from server 2 (top right).
 - The coding researcher observed the monitor tab on Aapanel as a result of testing 501 concurrent users with Apache JMeter, which was averaged with the data obtained from testing on real users (bottom left).
 - The technician explained the concept of RAM swap to the researchers (bottom right).

[Figure 14: Real User Penetration Test (501 Respondents) and Concurrent Load Simulation (501 JMeter Bots)]
(Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

The image above shows the system workload profile when facing dynamic interactions from 501 real users simultaneously. The stability of the on-premise architecture is reflected in the CPU Busy and SYS Load metrics, which are identical at 15.5%, indicating precise and efficient processing load distribution. RAM utilization of 31.8% with minimal SWAP usage (0.4%) proves that the 32 GB physical memory capacity is sufficient to handle human interaction traffic, including protocol handshakes and live chat activities, without paging to secondary storage, thus ensuring consistent system responsiveness at the sub-millisecond level.

In stress testing using Apache JMeter with a simulation of 501 bots (Figure below), the system showed more significant processing efficiency with CPU Busy at only 6.4% and SYS Load stagnant at 0.5%, confirming the web server's capability to handle massive HTTP request throughput atomically. An interesting technical phenomenon was observed in the increase in SWAP to 20.5% even though physical RAM was only 21.2% used; this indicates the operating system kernel's optimization mechanism, which moves passive background processes to virtual memory to prioritize physical resources for repetitive concurrent traffic from the bot testing scheme.

(Figure 15: Monitoring of 501 Simple Concurrent User Testing by Apache JMeter Feature)
 (Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

- a) The Summary Report feature in Apache JMeter with a screenshot generated during the 501 concurrent user test, which is still in the 500th process and has not been averaged with the built-in Apache JMeter feature (top left).
- b) The Result Tree feature is available with the results obtained from successful HTTP Requests for a total of 501 concurrent users in local testing (edulearn.sch.id) and one error in public testing (edulearn.asasmk.my.id) (top right).
- c) The Graph Results feature in Apache JMeter in public testing shows latency of 2952 ms, throughput of 256,419/minute, deviation of 2188, and average of 1267 (bottom left).
- d) Significant differences were found between the public and local tests, with the local test achieving a latency of only 209 ms, a throughput of 300,919/minute, a deviation of 91, and an average of 159 (bottom right).

(Figure 16: System Efficiency Analysis at Peak Concurrent User Load)
 (Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

- System & Computing Utilization (top left, top center, and top right corners): Peak system resource usage only reached 13.55% with CPU load at 25.85%, indicating that the EduLearn architecture has extensive headroom (remaining capacity). This proves the efficiency of web server orchestration in handling concurrent requests from 501 users without reaching the saturation threshold.
- Memory Management (bottom left corner): RAM usage of 14.26% shows the effectiveness of the 32 GB physical memory allocation. This low memory consumption reflects code optimization on the application side that is able to keep the memory footprint minimal even when accessed massively.
- Disk I/O Throughput (bottom center): Read activity (1349.60 KB/s), which is significantly higher than write activity (155.07 KB/s), validates the characteristics of LMS as a read-intensive application (retrieving materials/questions), where the system is able to respond quickly in delivering data from storage to users.
- Network I/O Dynamics (bottom right corner): Upstream activity reaching 138.33 KB/s represents content distribution (web assets/text) from the server to the client, while downstream (37.40 KB/s) records incoming data flow (student input). This ratio indicates the stability of the communication path between Cloudflare Tunnel and the local network.

(Figure 17: Analysis of Intensive Workload in DevOps System Integration)
 (Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

- a) Extreme Computational Saturation (upper left corner, upper middle, and upper right corner): There was a drastic surge in system load of up to 97.19% with CPU utilization reaching 99.64%. This phenomenon confirms that GitLab operations in Docker containers on Intel Xeon E3-1225 V5 (4 Core) processors are at a critical point (CPU Bound), where the entire processor instruction cycle is fully absorbed to run the GitLab background service.
- b) High Memory Reservation (bottom left corner): Memory consumption surged to 85.53%. This reflects GitLab's characteristics as an enterprise-level application that requires a large memory buffer for repository management and its internal database, which significantly limits the space for other application services on a single node.
- c) Disk I/O Escalation (bottom center): Write (11454.13 KB/s) and read (9658.80 KB/s) activities increased by thousands of percent compared to the first test, indicating the massive operational intensity of logs, databases, and container archiving processes, which could potentially trigger queues (I/O Wait) on the disk controller.
- d) Network Efficiency (bottom right corner): Despite the very high internal load, upstream network I/O remained under control at 135.51 KB/s, indicating that the main workload was on internal data processing (local computing) rather than external network transmission.

Appendix 6: EduLearn Website Interface

(Figure 18: Integrated Development Environment/IDE and Task Management)

(Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

- Task Repository Panel (top left): Representation of the digital task collection interface that facilitates the transmission of learning artifacts from students to the relevant class database.
- Profile Configuration Module (top center and bottom center): User digital identity management console that allows adjustment of account parameters and system personalization preferences.
- Filtered Communication Module (top right): Instant messaging navigation feature that implements class entity-based filtering algorithms to ensure coherence in inter-academic communication.
- Programming Instruction Panel (center left): Visualization of technical specifications and coding task parameters personalized by educators.
- Execution & Output Console (center right): A runtime environment component that displays the results of code compilation and execution in real time within a web-based architecture.
- Integrated Development Environment (bottom right): A web-based text editor designed for programming productivity, supporting direct syntax writing without dependence on external software.
- Class Initiation Interface (bottom left): Enrollment gateway that allows students to integrate into the learning ecosystem through class code authentication mechanism

(Figure 19: Student Academic Dashboard and Attendance Management)
 (Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

- a) Unified Authentication Portal (top left): An integrated login page that implements security protocols to verify access rights for three user roles: Students, Teachers, and Administrators.
- b) Central Student Dashboard (top right): A central control center that visualizes student academic status immediately after successful authentication.
- c) Attendance Recap Analysis (top center): An automated attendance reporting module that presents historical student absence data as a tool for self-evaluation of discipline.
- d) Many-to-One Communication Architecture (2nd row): Implementation of asynchronous communication channels that enable multiple student interactions with one accompanying teacher in the classroom ecosystem.
- e) Intra-Class Task Management (bottom left): A hierarchy of isolated task storage within class management, ensuring students can only access content after being validated as class members.
- f) Daily Reporting Dashboard (bottom center): A comprehensive panel that integrates attendance logs, daily activity reports, and calendar widgets as parameters for student time management.
- g) Member Directory Module (bottom right): Visualization of the list of participants in active classes, aimed at mapping the social and collaborative structure between students.

(Figure 20: Teacher Instructional and Learning Module Control)
(Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

- a) Class-Based Communication Navigation (left row 1): A message sorting interface that organizes conversation data based on class segmentation, optimizing teachers' workflow in responding to class dynamics.
- b) Instructional Metrics Console (top center): An executive dashboard for teachers that presents aggregated statistical data on the number of active classes, material inventory, and assessment effectiveness.
- c) One-to-Many Communication Architecture (left row 2 & last): An instant messaging interface that supports the transmission of mass instructions from teachers to all students, strengthening collaborative pedagogical coordination.
- d) Class Entity Dashboard Specifics (middle of 2nd row): In-depth visualization of the specific conditions of a curated class, including curriculum progress and participant status.
- e) Curriculum Injection Module (top right): A functional component for integrating new learning materials or module units into the established class architecture.
- f) Micro Configuration Parameters (right side of the second row): A class-specific (not global) settings console that allows teachers to modify rules, access restrictions, and internal class attributes.

Appendix 7: Break-Even Point Analysis

Then, on-premise architecture requires a large initial investment, but the following year's costs are only 5.6% of the annual costs of the cloud model (47.04 million from the recurring costs of on-premise divided by 840 million from the recurring costs of the cloud). The break-even point is calculated as follows:

$$\text{BEP}_{(\text{bulan})} = \frac{\text{CAPEX}}{\text{Biaya Cloud/bulan} - \text{OPEX On-Premise/bulan}}$$
$$\text{BEP} = \frac{\text{Rp58.700.000}}{\text{Rp70.000.000} - \text{Rp3.950.000}} \approx 0,89 \text{ bulan}$$

Appendix 8: Online Documentation

- i. Google Drive Folder Sharing:
<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1b9dXeCMIM54dkaC6B8yPZyoGsYXFYOAZ?usp=sharing>
 - a. Database dump: data_user_login.pdf
 - b. SOP: SOP and Testing Table EduLearn.pdf
 - c. Test data for 501 respondents: SYSTEM TEST DATA SUMMARY EDULEARN
 - d. Apache JMeter (public summary): summary-public- test.csv
 - e. Apache JMeter (local summary): summary-lokal.csv
- ii. Github: <https://github.com/Anggaaja15/edulearn>

Appendix 9: Flowchart

(Figure 21: Teacher Flowchart)
(Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

The flowchart in Figure 21 illustrates the workflow and navigation within the teacher interface of the EduLearn system. The process begins at the login page, where the system validates credentials (email/username and password) and ensures the user role is "teacher". Upon successful login, the system creates a session storing essential data such as user ID, username, name, email, and logged-in status, then directs the teacher to the main dashboard. This dashboard displays relevant statistical summaries, including the total number of classes taught, total students under supervision, total uploaded materials, and total assignments created. From here, teachers can access six main menus that support all teaching activities.

The first menu is Class Management, which allows teachers to create new classes by entering the class name, description, and schedule. The system then automatically generates a random banner (from 1-3 options) and a unique 8-character invitation code to be shared with students. Class data is stored in the database, and teachers can view class details including class information, materials, assignments, student lists, and forum activity. The second menu is Material Management, where teachers can upload learning materials through an upload form, which are saved to the

uploads/materi/ folder and recorded in the database. Teachers can also view and download previously uploaded materials. The third menu is Assignment Management, enabling teachers to add new assignments by completing data such as title, description, deadline, assignment type, and optional supporting files. The system validates the assignment type; if it is not a programming (PPLG) assignment, the file is uploaded to the uploads/tugas/ folder and the data is saved to the database. The fourth menu is Grading, where teachers can view assignment submission lists per task, monitor students who have and have not submitted, view grade statistics (average, maximum/minimum scores), download student assignments, and input grades via an AJAX mechanism with score validation (0-100 range). The grade saving process is performed transactionally, updating both the assignment_submissions and student_grades tables. The fifth menu is Student Management, which authorizes teachers to remove students from classes after validating class ownership. The sixth menu is Settings, allowing teachers to update their profile (name and email) and change their password using a password hashing mechanism for security. This entire workflow is designed to comprehensively support teachers in managing the learning process, from class administration and material provision to assignment distribution and student learning evaluation.

(Figure 22: Student Flowchart)
 (Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

The flowchart in Figure 22 illustrates the workflow and navigation within the student interface of the EduLearn system. The process begins at the student login page, followed by the main dashboard display which serves as the central control hub for student activities. From the dashboard, students have several main navigation options.

First, students can join a class by entering an invitation code obtained from the teacher; the system validates the code and enrolls the student in the appropriate class. After joining, students can access the class dashboard which displays various class-related information, including assignments, learning modules, and recent activities. Second, students can access the reporting and attendance feature, where clicking the attendance button records attendance data into the database managed by the admin. Third, students can view class data containing a list of all enrolled classes, and access class details which include teacher information, student lists, and assigned tasks. Fourth, students can access learning modules that must be completed in stages; the system tracks progress, allowing students to continue modules already started or begin new modules from the beginning. Fifth, students can upload assignments by selecting a file to submit, then clicking the send button to deliver the assignment to the teacher. Sixth, the live chat feature enables students to communicate directly with teachers, but this feature is only accessible after students have joined a class. All student activities, including assignment submissions and chat messages, are recorded in the teacher's database for monitoring and evaluation. The process concludes with the student logging out of the system, which redirects back to the initial login page.

(Figure 23: Admin Flowchart)
 (Source: Researcher's Personal Documentation)

The flowchart in Figure 23 illustrates the workflow and navigation within the administrator interface of the EduLearn system. The process begins at the admin login page. Upon successful credential verification, the system directs the admin to the main dashboard. From here, the admin can either choose to logout, which destroys the session and redirects back to the login page, or proceed to the main menu. The main menu provides access to five core management modules: Student Data, Teacher Data, Class Data, Grade Data, and System Settings. In the Student Data module, the admin can view lists of students per class and access individual details, including class history, grades, attendance records, and daily reports. The Teacher Data module displays a complete list of all teachers along with their performance statistics, such as the total number of classes taught, materials and assignments created, and students under their supervision.

The Class Data module presents all class information with details like the supervising teacher, student lists, and relevant statistics. The Grade Data module allows the admin to filter data based on class, type, and year, then displays a list of student grades. From this interface, the admin can view grade details, delete grade entries, or generate report files. Finally, the System Settings module contains functions for updating the admin profile (email, name, password) and performing database backups that can be saved to local storage. This entire workflow is designed to provide administrators with comprehensive control over managing all aspects of EduLearn system data and configurations.